

Dialogic Leadership as a Strategy to Reduce Quiet Quitting: Evidence from the Al-Anbar Health Department

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Abstract

The aim of this research is to identify the role that dialogue leadership plays in reducing quiet quitting, among a selected sample of administrative leaders in the Al-Anbar Health Department. And its hypothesis, a hypothetical scheme was developed through which the nature of the correlation and effect relationship between the research variables and its dimensions was determined, and the researchers used the analytical descriptive approach in order to reach the results, and the questionnaire was a major tool in collecting data and information related to the field aspect of the research, as the Al-Anbar health department was chosen as a field for research Through a sample of 86 administrative leaders out of the total research community of 110 leaders, as the valid forms for statistical analysis were 75 questionnaire. The research came out with a number of conclusions and recommendations that were consistent with its hypotheses, the most important of which The existence of a negative correlation and impact relationship between the variables of the study and its dimensions, and this confirms that the more graceful leadership is available in the organization, the research sample, the more this contributes for reducing its quiet quitting, and vice versa. The research concluded with number of recommendations that is considers necessary for the purpose of adopting them by the Al-Anbar health department.

Keywords: *Dialogue Leadership, Reducing Quiet Quitting, Al-Anbar Health Department.*

JEL Classification codes: *I15, D23, M1.*

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Introduction

Contemporary organizations face challenges resulting from the multiplicity of their tasks and activities, which puts them under the influence of environmental challenges and their associated events and repercussions. These organizations fall into adopting new organizational divisions and approving complex work rules and procedures in their implementation, as well as adopting new appointments that appear to support these organizations with new energy, fill vacancies and gaps, and enhance capabilities, and others is the emergence of unjustified increases and disabled competencies, coupled with the emergence of dependency among the work parties in a way that illustrates the phenomenon of laziness. These are early warning signs of low productivity and declining growth rates, which reveal many implications and extrapolation of many conclusions, namely the misuse of the organization's resources and the emergence of functional blocs to the point of immersion in bureaucracy. This led to the emergence of a problem for which the dialogue leadership seeks to develop effective solutions.

To determine the truth of the above, the University of Fallujah was chosen as a field of study. The current study is organized into four chapters. The initial chapter presented the empirical approach of the study, secondly the theoretical foundation, the third one the field aspect, and the fourth the research conclusion by presenting the most essential findings and recommendations attained by the research.

Study Problem

Production organizations in general and service organizations in particular face many accelerating developments and challenges in the field of communications and information technology, especially in Iraq's environment, which have imposed on these organizations the need to work on the process of change and organizational development in their various work and activities to keep pace with those developments, as well as the intensity of competition among organizations. In the face of those challenges, organizations have been forced to embrace many modern organizational leadership concepts that can formulate and implement various strategic directions, as well as identify what is known as dialogue leadership as a leadership style that emphasizes the importance of dialogue and communication in the decision-making process. It is a collaborative approach that involves listening, learning, and sharing with others to reach a common understanding.

In dialogic leadership, the leader seeks to create an environment in which everyone feels comfortable sharing their thoughts and ideas. The leader encourages open communication and is willing to listen to different points of view without judgment. This approach fosters a culture of respect, trust, and collaboration, which can lead to better decision-making and more innovative solutions. Accordingly, the intellectual dilemma of the study revolves around two aspects:

First: It is represented by adopting dialogue leadership as an inevitable means to reduce quiet quitting to achieve efficiency and effectiveness in activities and operations by encouraging and motivating workers and expanding their vision through others, as well as enhancing creative and innovative processes and employing them in the organization's practices and operations to contribute giving value to the organization and workers together to achieve excellence and creativity. The dialogic leader also recognizes that their perspective is not the only correct perspective and seeks to learn from others. They value diversity and inclusion and actively work to create opportunities for everyone to participate in the conversation.

Second: Dialogical leadership is an approach that focuses on people and emphasizes the importance of relationships, trust, and cooperation in achieving common goals. It is particularly effective in complex and uncertain environments where not a single individual has all the answers, and where diversity of perspectives is necessary for success that indicates complementarity and

interdependence among all the overall strategic components to achieve a full understanding of the processes and strategies that contribute to the organization's performance excellence.

The problem of the study can be clarified by raising the following key question: What is the role and impact of the dialogue leadership in limiting quiet quitting in the Anbar Health Department? From this point of view, the study raises a series of sub-questions that reflect the problem of the study in the organizations discussed as follows: -

1. What are the attitudes of the individuals surveyed towards the study variables in the researched organization?
2. To what extent are all dimensions of collaborative leadership available in the researched organization?
3. Do all dimensions of the dialogue leadership affect the limitation of quiet quitting?
4. Do the answers of the study sample members in the researched organization differ regarding the variables and dimensions of the study?

The Research Importance

The importance of the study stems from the importance of the variables of the current study, the topic it addresses, and the location chosen for it, which is represented by the Department of Al-Anbar Health. The importance is reflected in two aspects, cognitive and field, as follows:

Cognitive aspect

- a. The scarcity and limitations of the studies concerned with studying the variables and dimensions of the study and the relationship between them. According to the researcher's knowledge, there is no study at the local or Arab level that combines the variables and dimensions of the current study in a single hypothetical scheme.
- b. The importance of the present study is reflected in preparing a theoretical cognitive framework for current study variables, which is the dialogue leadership and (silent) resignation as well as the introduction of a cognitive accumulation that is a starting point and an incentive for other researchers to enrich this topic in future studies.

Field aspect

- a. The research attempts to measure and diagnose the reality of the variables and dimensions of the study as a necessity for the researched organization to know and measure through the presentation of the trends of the individual's answers.
- b. Studying the variables of dialogue leadership in the organization under investigation leads to determining the required level of positive influence in reducing quiet quitting.
- c. The results of the current study can be used to develop the organization's research courses of work, as well as provide some suggestions for researchers to undertake several future studies regarding the current study variables.

Research Objectives

By identifying the present study's difficulty and the absence of studies relating the research factors and their value, the study's major goal, which is to test the relationship between the independent variable represented by dialogue leadership and quiet quitting, in addition to achieving a set of goals as follows:

1. Identifying the presence of the dimensions of dialogue leadership in the researched organization and achieving a reduction in quiet quitting

2. Identifying the trends and nature of relationships that link the researched variables and their sub-dimensions in the researched organization.
3. Providing several recommendations and proposals that can be used to determine the role of dialogue leadership in reducing quiet quitting in the organization under study.
4. Identifying the discrepancy in the research sample participants' responses regarding a variables and dimensions of a study in the researched organization.

Research Hypotheses

To test the relationships contained in the hypothetical research scheme, the following hypotheses were identified:

1. The primary crucial hypothesis: it is a statistically important relationship between dialogue leadership and quiet quitting in terms of their dimensions at the general level and the component dimensions, which are as follows

1. It represents a significant statistical relationship between the active listening dimension and quiet quitting.
2. It is a significant statistical connection between the originality dimension and quiet quitting.
3. It represents a significant statistical link between the cooperation dimension and quiet quitting.
4. It is a significant statistical connection between the empowerment dimension and quiet quitting.

The second essential hypothesis is the idea that conversation leadership has a substantial, statistically significant influence on quiet quitting in terms of their dimensions on both the general and smaller dimension stages, according to the following:

1. It represents a significant statistical relationship between the active listening dimension and quiet quitting.
2. There is a statistically significant relationship between the originality dimension and quiet quitting.
3. There is a statistically significant relationship of influence between the dimension of inclusiveness and quiet quitting.
4. There is a statistically significant relationship between the empowerment dimension and quiet quitting.

Methodology

Research Tools

1. Data collecting techniques

In order to achieve the study aims and evaluate the hypotheses put forward, statistical procedures are used to collect data and information, according to the following:

- a. The theoretical aspect: In addressing the theoretical frameworks of the current research, researchers relied on several sources, which are Arabic and foreign literature from books, dissertations, university letters, and research published in scientific journals and websites.
- b. The practical aspect: In covering the practical aspect of the research, reliance was placed on the application form, because it is the primary instrument for gathering data and information linked to the research's field component . This questionnaire was developed by reviewing the literature related to the research topic, and then accuracy and objectivity were taken into account

in formulating its vocabulary. After adjustments, the questionnaire's final version contained two primary variables, which are dialogue leadership and quiet quitting. Every of those variables has a set of components, as indicated in Table 1, that illustrates the questionnaire's structure.

Table 1. Distribution of Phrases and Formulated Questions on the Research Variables and Dimensions

No.	Main variables	Sub-variables	Sequence in the questionnaire	Item no.	Sources
1	Personal info.	Sex	1	-	Researcher
		Qualification	2	-	
		Age	3	-	
		Service	4	-	
2	Dialogue leadership	Active listening	1-3	3	Taylor, (2017:9) Rozak, <i>et al.</i> , (2021:158) Mineo, (2014:2)
		Originality	4-6	3	
		Cooperation	7-9	3	
		Empowerment	10-12	3	
3	Quiet quitting	Job burnout	13-15	3	Al-Battani, (2006: 23) Devaro, (2016:15) Najim, (2022):494-495
		Poor dealing with others	16-18	3	
		low production	19-21	3	
		Poor coordination	22-24	3	

Source: designed by the Research Workers On the basis of the findings of the final questionnaire for research.

2. Testing the validity and reliability of the questionnaire

It indicates the ability of the questionnaire to measure what it was designed for, and this is one of the most important conditions that must be met in building standards (Hassoun & Al-Douri, 2022). The absence of this condition means that the scale is not valid and its results cannot be relied upon. The study questionnaire, with its authorized criteria, has been subjected to the following validity and reliability tests:

- a. Evaluating the questionnaire before distributing it (measuring perceived validity): the questionnaire is provided to various arbitrators who provide feedback on the validity of its paragraphs in order to achieve the highest degree of correctness in its design.
- b. Questionnaire testing after distribution, reliability assessment: The Cron-Nbach alpha technique, which is one of the most extensively used statistical methods in this particular field, is used to calculate the results of this test. The Cron-Nbach alpha value was calculated and was found to be (81), this is an excellent proportion for research and reflects the questionnaire's stability.

Statistical Techniques Utilized in Data Analysis

Based on the research trends and its intellectual and philosophical implications, and to prove the validity of its hypotheses, to evaluate data related to the field element of the research, the statistical analysis tool (24. SPSS, V) is applied. These instruments are classed as follows:

1. Cronbach alpha test to ascertain the validity and reliability of the questionnaire items and their internal consistency.
2. Arithmetic means, standard deviations, and coefficient of variation between the study variables and their dimensions.

3. Correlation coefficient: Pearson correlation coefficient to determine the strength of the association between the study variables and their dimensions.

4. Simple linear regression analysis to show the effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable.

Limits of Research

1. Spatial limit: The research uses quiet quitting as its field which is within the borders of the governorate's municipality.
2. Human limitations: The study covered a sample of administrative leaders in quiet quitting.
3. Time limits: The research extended from 10/2/2022 to 1/5/2023.

Organizational Description and Justifications for Selecting

1. Description of The Research Community and Sample

Quiet quitting represents a field for our current research, and the research population consists of a sample of administrative leaders that included all of the assistant hospital directors, heads of departments, and divisions, who numbered (110) administrative leaders. As for the research sample, it was extracted according to Stephen Thompson's equation, and it amounted to (86) leaders, after checking the retrieved questionnaires, (11) questionnaires were excluded, as the number of questionnaires suitable for statistical analysis became (75) questionnaires and Table 2 contains a brief summary to the study sample arrangement.

Table 2. A Simplified Definition of the Research Sample Organization

Organization (Research Sample)	Date Of Establishment	Employees No.	Doctors No.	Number Of Administrative Leaders (Society)	Sample
Quiet Quitting	1978	20371	1494	110	86

Source: Designed by the Research Workers

Justifications for Selecting the Study Field

Identifying the field in which research is being conducted is crucial for research in science, as proper field selection helps substantially to the validity of findings and the evaluating of hypotheses. Through the modern orientation of organizations, the research believes that there is an urgent need to employ the dimensions of dialogue leadership among the administrative leaders in the organization that is the research sample, in a way that leads to reducing quiet quitting. In light of the above, the following are the justifications for selecting the field of research:

- a. The research's nature and aims are aligned with the facts of health organizations in terms of the nature of the activity they practice.
- b. The importance of the vital role played by quiet quitting in showing medical care to all the people of the governorate.
- c. Medical care organizations have administrative leaders with academic qualifications capable of providing appropriate solutions to the health crises that the country is going through.
- d. A high organizational culture in health organizations enables us to obtain the necessary information for the success of research.

Theoretical Framework

The Concept of Dialogue Leadership

Dialogue leadership is one of the effective solutions adopted by contemporary organizations to confront environmental challenges, which enables them to maintain their competitive position and market position for the longest possible period, and also plays a major role in achieving organizational success. Ljungblom (2012: 59) defined it as behaviors that add or create value to the organization. Emilian & Emilian (2013: 409) see that dialogue leadership is a set of behaviors and characteristics that focus on speed in completing tasks, raising the morale of workers, increasing their desire to work, and originality in dealing with environmental variables to achieve a good reputation for the organization.

Dombrowski & Mielke (2014: 570) see it as an organized way to carry out work correctly through mutual respect and active listening between the leader and subordinates to achieve outstanding performance. Puvanasvaran et al (2009: 930) added that a leader with agile behavior is characterized by positive behaviors, including helping individuals, respecting their opinions, focusing on the course of work, as well as having a future vision, clear goals, and continuous commitment. (Aij, 2016:34)states that it is a systematic approach for the long-term installation and continual development of lean production methods that highlights the collaboration between staff and leaders. to complete the work assigned accurately and objectively, by focusing on customers in all production processes, as well as the long-term development of employees and leaders. From the perspective of decision-making, Attar & Abdu1, 2020:183 defined it as leadership that enables the leader to make wise and effective decisions amid a complex and rapidly changing environment. Researchers believe that dialogue leadership is an integrated approach through which the leader seeks to influence the behavior of individuals and incite their sense of belonging to the organization in a way that contributes to achieving its goals and objectives in the best way.

The Importance of Dialogue Leadership

Leadership is the basic foundation for the success and continuity of any organization that seeks to achieve excellence in performance and win the competition. (Al-Hariri, 17:2008) pointed out that the importance of collaborative leadership stems from its being an effective tool for linking individuals and available resources in the organization to achieve certain goals, as well as its impact on human behavior in general and administrative behavior in particular. (Hussein and Al-Zubaidi, 2021: 90) he believes that the importance of collaborative leadership represents the main driver of all the successes achieved by organizations, whether at the local or global level, and its role is also evident through continuous support to improve and invest its human resources in the best way, which allows them to maintain its competitive advantage for as long as possible.

While Rashwan (2010: 87) emphasized that the importance of dialogue leadership is represented by the following points:

1. Spreading the spirit of brotherhood and love among the members of the groups that make up the organization.
2. It helps the cohesion of the organization's members and intensifies their efforts to achieve common interests.
3. Determine the goals to be achieved according to the necessary plans and programs.
4. Promoting effective self-listening of the organization's members and removing the fear and anxiety they face when carrying out the required tasks.

Attar & Abdul (2020: 183) believe that collaborative leadership creates favorable conditions for followers to reveal their knowledge and abilities and use them effectively, as well as encouraging

creativity that contributes to finding modern methods for designing products. (Abdullah et al., 2021: 55) confirmed that collaborative leadership gives the organization a culture of agility that increases its response to environmental changes. Researchers believe that the importance of collaborative leadership is evident in representing the basic rule for the success and sustainability of any organization that seeks to reach the best levels of achieving profits winning the competition, and taking steps closer to excellence in providing products to meet customer requirements without excessive routine and complexity in performing tasks.

Dimensions of Dialogue Leadership

Many researchers (2012:330, Taylor, 2017:9) (McKenzie & Aitken) (2021:158, Rozak, et al) have indicated that the dimensions of dialogue leadership are (speed, authenticity, empowerment, cooperation, and follow-up technology). The current study relied on the following dimensions (active listening, originality, cooperation, and empowerment) due to their consistency with the sub-dimensions of the responding variable on the one hand and with the field of study on the other hand.

1. Active Listening

The success achieved by leadership in its field of work undoubtedly depends on its ability to create high levels of confidence among working individuals. This procedure contributes to increasing the individual's connection with leadership and thus enhances aspects of organizational success (Mine 2014:2). Thresson & Ostman, 2017:30, added that the leadership's possession of high confidence in its capabilities enables them to carry out the tasks and duties required of them correctly in the normal manner, as well as in critical and exceptional circumstances that cannot tolerate delay. Researchers believe that effective listening represents the link that connects the leader to his followers and is a direct cause of all the successes achieved by organizations in all fields.

2. Originality

This concept emerged as a response to the organizational conditions that prevailed during the past era, which witnessed intense competition between organizations at all levels. This prompted the leaders of organizations to the necessity of renewal and change in the human resources environment and developing their skills to make them more committed to the requirements of their new job roles by providing performance that exceeds expectations (Hajira, 18:2020), (Zainab and Fatima, 2022:2) added that flexible leadership allows the organization to quickly adapt to unexpected environmental changes and crises.

Researchers believe that originality enables the organization to respond directly to everything new and distinctive, and this procedure contributes to the success of the organizations and enables them to achieve their future goals.

3. Cooperation

Great dreams are not realized and cannot be transformed into reality through the effort of one individual, but depend on collective action by empowering subordinate individuals and giving them the power to be creative in their work. From this standpoint, agile leaders involve all individuals working on the project, and the reason for this is that organizations in the third millennium have no boundaries, which requires the necessity of everyone's cooperation (Hajira, 2020: 34). Al-Issawi added, 117:2022 that the method of command and control is no longer applied, and that giving powers to working individuals makes them feel strong and empowered that enables them to provide the best results for their organizations. Researchers believe that cooperation is the path of dialogue leadership that reduces the difficulties facing organizations while performing tasks and duties and increases their ability to achieve their future aspirations.

4. Empowerment

It is one of the positive aspects that interactive leadership focuses on and which adds value to the organization, as it enables leaders and subordinate individuals to accomplish the work assigned to them with precision and mastery and to make strategic decisions that achieve the best achievement for the organization (Al-Tijani, 2019: 15). Zainab and Fatima, 2:2022, added that efficient leadership is leadership that can keep pace with developments in light of sudden changes and crises, as well as contribute to solving problems automatically.

Empowerment gives the organization's management the ability to operate effectively in complex and uncertain cases, as well as optimal resource use that maximizes the benefit of the organization and its personnel.

Quiet Quitting (A Theoretical Introduction)

The concept of quiet quitting

Quiet quitting is a negative phenomenon resulting from slackness and poor dealings with others, which reflects negatively on low productivity and low rates of organizational growth. If we look closely at these indicators, we will find that they are the result of several reasons. Job stagnation is due to the lack of legislation and the interference of policies that lead to the imposition of unjustified appointments that cause an increase in the number of workers while poor dealing with others is due to the dependence of workers on each other due to weak coordination, which leads to low productivity in the organization, i.e. a low ratio of inputs to the ratio of outputs (Khalif, 2012: 129).

Mohammed, et al. 494-495: 2022, defined quiet quitting as the increase in the number of employees working in the organization's departments and branches without the actual need for them, and this leads to an increase in the organization's general expenses through an increase in the wages and salaries paid without increasing productivity (Fakhry, Alkhazraje, & Saleh, 2024). Researchers believe that quiet quitting indicates an inflated organizational structure, low productivity, and weak coordination, and this is a clear indication of the organization's decline and its inability to exploit the available opportunities. Organizational agility is a strategic choice that must be adhered to so that the organization does not lose opportunities, waste resources, dissipate energies, and degrade the organization's value considerations.

Dimensions of Quiet Quitting

By reviewing many previous studies (Al-Battani, 2006: 23) (Devaro 2016:15) (Najim, 2022:494-495), it was found that the dimensions of quiet quitting include job burnout, poor dealings with others, and a feeling of low production. The current study decided to add a dimension of poor coordination to the dimensions mentioned above to be more appropriate with the sub-dimensions of the independent variable as well as being consistent with the field of study. The following is a presentation of each of these dimensions:

1. Job Burnout

Inflation is one of the economic and social phenomena that tamper with the country's national economy and cause major imbalances. This phenomenon has spread in a large number of countries in the world, especially developing countries, and developed countries are not immune to it. Its causes are due to multiple structural imbalances and external shocks, as it has turned into a global phenomenon that trying to control is not easy.

Al-Battani, 2006: 23 defined job burnout as a situation in which the number of employees in the organization is greater than the actual need for work, and this leads to a decline in the employee's level of performance and decreased productivity. Al-Barrak, 1997:175, defines it as the increase in

the number of workers and organizations and the accompanying increase in the number of jobs at rates that exceed the actual and expected work needs of those organizations. Researchers believe that job burnout is a type of unemployment and the most dangerous, as individuals work but do not produce anything, and it leaves negative effects on organizations such as a low level of productivity for the individual worker, failure to exploit available resources and energies, as well as the inflation of organizational structures and the emergence of many administrative problems.

Its causes are due to the weakness of administrative systems and their inconsistency with developments in the field of management, and behavioral reasons, including the desire of managers to increase the number of employees to indicate the importance of their work, as well as personal relationships that play a major role in creating unnecessary jobs and appointing people who do not have the required skills to complete the work.

2. Poor Dealing with Others

The concept of misdealing with others expresses the negative behaviors that individuals emit as a result of their lack of responsibility (Charbonneau et al., 2017:18). Liden (2004:285) believes that it indicates a lack of motivation among working individuals and the feeling of each team member that he is not responsible for the result that has been achieved (Fakhry, Alkhazraje, & Saleh, 2024). As for Devaro (2016:15), he believes that mistreatment of others indicates an individual's deviation from performing a particular job as a result of personal interests and not obtaining sufficient material incentives, that is, the individual's feeling that his efforts are not compatible with the wage or salary that he receives (Fakhry, Alkhazraje, & Saleh, 2024). These factors make the individual deliberately waste time and not complete the tasks assigned to him correctly (Fakhry, Alkhazraje, & Saleh, 2024), for psychological reasons or organizational factors. Fischer et al. 2011:21 noted that one of the most important ways of addressing the mishandling of others is to choose the right man in the right place as well as to follow an open-door policy that enables managers to listen to the problems and pressures faced by individuals working while doing business to eliminate them. Researchers have defined mistreatment of others as indicating the tendency of individuals to provide less effort when the size of the group increases. This is addressed by giving the individual the freedom to express his ideas, listen to them, and adopt good ideas that serve the organization.

3. Feeling Low in Production

The concept of low productivity expresses a low ratio of outputs compared to inputs, and this is due to weak management and its inability to employ individuals who possess the skills and academic qualifications that can add new value to the organization (Khalif, 2012: 129). While (Najim, 494, 2022:495) believes that modern organizations seek to increase their productivity by devoting the concept of productivity to their workers, and urging them to provide their best performance to achieve excellence, and this is the essence of superior organizations globally. Researchers believe that low productivity indicates a decline in the productivity of the working individual beyond the required level as a result of weak academic qualifications and a lack of motivation and achievement among the working individuals due to their lack of a sense of responsibility (Fakhry, Alkhazraje, & Saleh, 2024). This leads to the organization's decline in growth and its inability to properly exploit the available opportunities and ultimately causes the organization to decline from its competitive position.

4. Poor Coordination

It refers to the organization's inability to arrange the available human and financial resources according to a clear system based on identifying the various functions and tasks required to achieve the organization's ultimate goal (BIMIC, 1998:7). Organization is the opposite. It means defining the framework within which efforts are formed to achieve goals, and it includes defining each of

the authorities, responsibilities, and relationships between people within the organization to work to achieve its goals (Dagher and Saleh, 2008: 66).

Researchers believe that weak coordination leads to a lack of unified efforts and actions due to multiple leaders and a lack of unity of leadership. This leads to the decline of the organization and its inability to achieve common goals because coordination is not achieved through control and orders according to the hierarchy of authority, but it also depends on unifying the forces of organizational teachings, work spirit, and morale.

Results and Discussion

First: Describe and diagnose the scope of the study and its elements. The first segment comprises analyzing the nature of the respondents' beliefs regarding the research's primary variables, namely (the importance of dialogue leadership in decreasing quiet quitting), in addition to the aspects which comprise these dimensions, including the following:

Firstly, analyzing and explaining the dimensions of the research sample organization's dialogue leadership.

The mean score, standard deviations, coefficient of variation, and relative importance in Table 3 with relation to the study's sample positions on given that the hypothesized mean is equal to (3) on the area of the scale, what are the aspects of dialogue leadership at general level. According to the findings, the aspects of dialogue leadership at the general level attained a mean score of (3.24), which is an average level. This is a good indicator in confirming the need for the organization under study to adopt the dimensions of dialogue leadership to reduce quiet quitting in their organization. As a result, the standard deviation (0.83) and coefficient of variation (25.4%) suggest that there is a low proportion of dispersion in the study sample's responses, indicating that they have a clear understanding of the concept of dialogue leadership and its dimensions. The effective listening dimension, with a mean of (3.25), with a standard deviation (0.82), and a coefficient of variation of (25%), is one of the most important dimensions that helped to enhancing the dialogue leadership variable.

Table 3. Research Sample Responses to the Dimensions of Dialogue Leadership

No	Dialogue Leadership Dimensions	Mean Score	Standard Deviation	Variation Coefficient	Relative Importance
1	Active listening	3.25	0.82	0.250	Average
2	Originality	3.02	0.86	0.287	Average
3	Cooperation	3.23	0.86	0.252	Average
4	Empowerment	3.42	0.76	0.222	Average
Total index		3.24	0.83	0.254	Average

Source: Designed by the Research Workers on the Basis on the Results of the Electronic Calculator (SPSS).

Second: The description and diagnosis of the dimensions of quiet quitting are evident from the arithmetic means, standard deviations, Table 4 shows the coefficient of variance and relative relevance of the research sample's locations on the dimensions of quiet quitting, assuming that the hypothesized mean is equal to (3) on the scale. According to the findings, the dimensions of quiet quitting at the general level attained a mean score of (2.60), that is considered average. The standard deviation is (0.89) and the coefficient of variation is (0.34), indicating that there is a small dispersion in the study sample's replies, indicating that they have a thorough understanding of the meaning of

quiet quitting and its dimensions. The job weariness dimension, with a mean (2.71), standard deviation (0.96), and coefficient of variation (35.4%), is one of the most important dimensions that helped to enhancing the quiet quitting variable.

Table 4. Responses of the Research Sample Regarding the Dimensions of Quiet Quitting

No	Dialogue Leadership Dimensions	Arithmetic Mean	Standard Deviation	Variation Coefficient	Relative Importance
1	Job Burnout	2.71	0.91	0.344	Average
2	Poor Dealing With Others	2.51	0.84	0.341	Average
3	Feeling low production	2.41	0.75	0.331	Average
Total index		2.56	0.81	0.342	Average

Source: Designed by the Research Workers Basis on the Results of the Electronic Calculator (SPSS).

Testing the Relationships Contained in the Research Scheme

General Relationship Between Dialogue Leadership Dimensions and Quiet Quitting

The content of this relationship represents verification of the first essential hypothesis's validity, as the data in Table 5 indicate the existence of a negative correlation with an important significance between the dimensions of dialogue leadership and quiet quitting in the organization of the research sample at the overall level, with a correlation coefficient of (-0.79) at Significant level (0.05). This result supports the validity of the first essential hypothesis, as the negative indicates the inverse relationship between the two variables, that is, the greater the application of dialogue leadership in the organization sampled by the study, the more this leads to reducing organizational inflation and vice versa.

Table 5. Results of the Connection between the Two Variables of Dialogue Leadership and Quiet Quitting at the General Level

Explanatory Variable	Dialogue Leadership
Responsive Variable Quiet Quitting	-0.79

Source: Results of the electronic calculator (SPSS) at a significance level (0.05). N=75

The sub-dimension connection between the dimensions of dialogue leadership and quiet quitting. Table 6 reveals the following by studying the correlation coefficients between the aspects of dialogue leadership and quiet quitting:

- a. It shows a negative significant connection between the active listening dimension and quiet quitting, with a correlation value of (72) at the level of significance (0.05).
- b. It represents a negative significant connection between the dimension of originality and quiet quitting, with correlation value (-0.77) at the level of significance (0.05).
- c. It represents a negative significant relationship between the dimension of cooperation and quiet quitting, with correlation value (-070) at the level of significance (0.05).
- d. It shows a negative significant connection between the dimension of empowerment and quiet quitting, with correlation value (-0.69) at the level of significance (0.05).

Table 6. Results of the Connection between the Dimensions of Dialogue Leadership and Quiet Quitting with the General Level of the Sample

Explanatory Variable Responsive Variable	Dimensions of Dialogue Leadership			
	Active Listening	Originality	Cooperation	Empowerment
Quiet Quitting	-0.72	-0.77	-0.70	-0.69

Source: Results of the electronic calculator (SPSS) at a significance level (0.05). N=75

These relationships indicate that the more dimensions of dialogue leadership are available in the organization itself, the more this contributes to reducing its organizational aggrandizement, through the effective listening dimension, the originality dimension, the cooperation dimension, and the empowerment dimension. Basis on the previous results of connections at the macro levels, the first main hypothesis was proven correct.

Influence Connections between the Research Variables

Table 7 shows the presence of an important inverse effect of the dimensions of dialogue leadership in reducing quiet quitting at a significant level (0.05), as the value of the Beta coefficient reached (-0.79) and the calculated (F) value reached (347.703) at two degrees of freedom (1.74) and a significance level (0.05), which indicates the significance of the second main hypothesis, and what confirms this significance is the value of (T), which reached (18.647-). The value of the coefficient of determination (0.640) (R^2), is a descriptive measure used to explain the usefulness of the regression equation. This indicates that the dimensions of dialogue leadership clarify the actual value of the responsive variable (64) it is represented by quiet quitting, which confirms the acceptance of the second main hypothesis.

Table 7. The Relationship of Influence of Dialogue Leadership Dimensions in Reducing Quiet Quitting at the General Level

Explanatory Variable Responsive Variable	Quiet Quitting			
	B ₁	R ²	Calculated F	Calculated T
Dialogue Leadership Dimensions Dimensions Combined	-0.79	0.640	347,703	-18.647

Source: Results of the electronic calculator (SPSS) at a significance level (0.05). N=75, df (1. 74), *P≤ 0.05.

Evaluating the Impact Relationships at the Micro Level

The effect of active listening in reducing quiet quitting

Table 8 shows a significant inverse effect of the active listening dimension in reducing quiet quitting at the level of significance (0.05), with the value of the coefficient (Beta) (-0.72) and the calculated (F) value reached (172.739) at two freedom degrees (1.74) and a significance level (0.05), this illustrates the importance of the second primary hypothesis at the first dimension level, and what emphasizes the significance is the value of (T), which reached (-9.447), and the coefficient of determination's value ((0.518) (R)). This indicates that the active listening dimension explains (51.8%) of the responding variable represented by quiet quitting, and this confirms the acceptance of the second major hypothesis at the first dimension level.

The effect of the originality dimension in reducing quiet quitting

Table 8 shows a significant inverse effect of the originality dimension in reducing quiet quitting at the level of significance (0.05), as the value of the coefficient (Beta) reached (0.77) and the

calculated (F) value reached (183.706) at two freedom degrees (1.74) and a significance level (0.05), this demonstrates the relevance of the second major hypothesis at the level of the second dimension, and what confirms this significance is the value of (T), which reached (-12.314), and the value of the coefficient of determination (0.592) (2). This indicates that the active listening dimension explains (59.2%) of the responding variable represented by quiet quitting, and this confirms the acceptance of the second major hypothesis at the second dimension level.

The effect of the cooperation component in reducing quiet quitting

Table 8 shows a significant inverse effect of the cooperation dimension in reducing quiet quitting at the level of significance (0.05), as the value of the Beta coefficient (-0.70) and the calculated (F) value reached (168.132) at two freedom degrees (1.74) and a significance level (0.05), which indicates the significance of the second primary hypothesis at the third dimension level, and what emphasizes the significance is the value of (T), which (-7.215), and the value of the coefficient of determination (R²) (0.490). This demonstrates that the active listening component reflects the value of (49%) of the responding variable represented by quiet quitting, and this confirms the acceptance of the second major hypothesis at the third dimension level.

The effect of the empowerment dimension on reducing quiet quitting

Table 8 shows a significant inverse effect of the empowerment dimension on reducing quiet quitting at an important level (0.05), as the value of the Beta coefficient was (-0.66) and the calculated F value was (165.233) at two freedom degrees (1.74) at the level of significance (0.05). This shows the significance of the second major hypothesis at the fourth dimension level, and what confirms this significance is the value of (T), which reached (6784), and the value of the coefficient of determination (R²) (0.466). This confirms the acceptance of the second primary hypothesis at the fourth dimension level.

Table 8. Results of the Influence Relationship at the Micro Level

Explanatory variable Responsive variable	Quiet quitting			
	B ₁	R ²	Calculated F	Calculated T
Dialogue leadership dimensions	-0.71	0.528	174.739	-9.437
Active listening	-0.69	0.582	185.706	-12.214
Cooperation	-0.72	0.489	169.132	-7.255
Empowerment	-0.66	0.466	165.233	-6.784

Source: Results of the electronic calculator (SPSS) at a significance level (0.05). N=75, df (1. 74), * 0P ≤ 0.05.

Conclusions

According to the descriptive statistical analysis, the dialogue leadership variable at the whole and component levels attained an average level of significance. This result explains that the employees of the surveyed organization have a firm understanding of the notion of dialogue leadership and its value in the workplace.

The descriptive statistical analysis findings of the quiet quitting variable at the general and the components levels indicates that it reached an average level of importance. This result is explained by the fact that the organization's management that is the research sample seeks to get rid of the quiet quitting to provide better services.

The statistical study reveals a substantial negative connection between dialogue leadership and quiet quitting at both the general and components levels. These findings indicate that the reduction of

quiet quitting depends heavily on dialogue leadership, as the more the organization sampled in the research tends towards providing dialogue leadership, the more this contributes to reducing quiet quitting that affects the organization's current and future performance.

The results of the influence relationship at the general and components levels indicates that the adoption of the dimensions of dialogue leadership by the organization in the research sample has a moral effect on reducing its quiet quitting, as the keenness of the employees of the researched organization to provide dialogue leadership in the work environment will contribute to enhancing its operational efficiency and enabling it to achieve its future goals. This reinforces the theoretical aspect of the research.

Recommendations

The necessity of employing the dimensions of dialogue leadership in the organization, the research sample, which are represented by the dimensions of effective listening, originality, cooperation, and empowerment to reduce the negative indicators left by quiet quitting in the field under study. This procedure requires the presence of administrative leaders with a great deal of responsibility.

Urge the management of the research organization to attract scientific competencies from doctors and staff with high scientific qualifications to benefit from their expertise to enhance the organization's position in society.

Finding a common vision among administrative leaders regarding quiet quitting, that quiet quitting is a negative indicator that causes a decline in the level of services provided by the organization under study to its customers, through developing a clearly defined strategy that enables it to exploit its resources positively and effectively, if not optimally.

Adopt a training policy that allows staff to acquire new skills and expertise in disciplines that are currently much needed by urging staff to participate in modern training programs.

Activating the role of administrative oversight to ensure field follow-up of all medical departments and divisions in the organization, the research sample, by identifying all the negatives and addressing them, which enhances the organization's success in the labor market.

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